

Rule of Law in the Global Innovation Index

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In the Global Innovation Index (GII), the "Rule of Law" variable represents a key indicator for assessing the degree of legality and the effectiveness of the rule of law in a country. It measures the efficiency and impartiality of legal institutions, adherence to regulations, and the ability to enforce property rights and contracts. A strong and reliable legal system contributes to creating a favorable environment for innovation by providing legal protection for ideas and inventions, thereby encouraging investment in research and development. The presence of fair and accessible justice reduces the risks associated with business activities and promotes market confidence. The concept of Rule of Law is also closely tied to transparency and reducing corruption; in countries where the legal system is transparent and functions correctly, businesses and innovators can operate more securely. This GII element is especially important because it allows for comparing different countries based on their legal and institutional stability, a crucial factor for the attractiveness and sustainability of innovative investments. In summary, a high score in the Rule of Law variable indicates a robust legal environment that facilitates innovation and fosters economic development. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Rule of Law in 2022. The data on the "Rule of Law" variable in the 2022 Global Innovation Index highlights significant differences among countries in terms of the effectiveness of the rule of law, a key element in supporting innovation. At the top of the ranking is Finland with the maximum score of 100, followed by other Nordic countries like Norway and Denmark, and countries like New Zealand, Singapore, and Switzerland. These countries are characterized by strong, transparent, and reliable legal systems, where regulations are applied fairly and there is a high degree of trust in institutions. Legal stability in these nations ensures effective protection of property rights and

regulatory security that fosters a positive environment for innovation and entrepreneurship. Generally, European and East Asian countries dominate the top positions, with countries like Austria, Sweden, and the Netherlands scoring above 90. This reflects a commitment to maintaining solid legal institutions and applying laws transparently, a factor that promotes both foreign and local investments. Canada and Australia, with scores of 89 and 88.9, respectively, also confirm the importance of a stable legal system in attracting innovation and developing advanced business activities. In contrast, many developing countries and those in politically unstable situations show very low scores. Among these, we find African countries such as Madagascar (23.2), Nigeria (25), and Niger (31.9), which face evident challenges in enforcing laws and maintaining a transparent legal system. Such limitations can significantly hinder economic development and the ability to attract investment, as legal instability and corruption-related risks deter innovative enterprises. Countries like Iraq, with an extremely low score of 0.6, highlight severe legal and institutional crises where the rule of law is almost non-existent. Emerging countries such as India (45.6) and China (44.5) are positioned in the middle of the rankings, suggesting progress toward greater institutional stability but also significant challenges in ensuring uniform law enforcement. For China, in particular, the low score indicates that, despite being a leader in many areas of technological innovation, there are still relevant issues related to property rights and regulatory transparency. The United States, with a score of 81.6, shows a lower value than top-ranking European countries, reflecting some concerns about the legal system and disparities in law enforcement while maintaining a solid position compared to the global average. Italy, with a score of 52.3, occupies a mid-lower position, suggesting problems related to the judicial system's slowness and inefficiencies that can discourage investment. In summary, the data demonstrate how a high level of Rule of Law is closely correlated with a favorable context for innovation. The lack of legal stability, as observed in many emerging or unstable economies, represents a significant obstacle to economic development. However, the progress made by some developing countries indicates that improving the rule of law can offer substantial opportunities to stimulate innovation and economic growth, making this variable a focal point for economic policy worldwide.

Rule of Law Between 2013 and 2022. Analyzing Rule of Law data in the Global Innovation Index from 2013 to 2022 reveals interesting trends that highlight the divide between countries with increasing and declining rule of law and institutional stability, a fundamental element for supporting innovation and attracting investments. Some countries have shown significant improvements, while others have experienced a marked deterioration. Among the top-performing countries are Côte d'Ivoire, Ecuador, and Uzbekistan, which have seen increases of 131%, 93%, and 90%, respectively. These increases can be attributed to legal and institutional reforms that have strengthened the judiciary and reduced corruption, creating a safer environment for business. Nations like Kenya and Nepal have also made notable progress, improving their positions and demonstrating how commitment to legality can contribute to economic stability. For emerging countries like these, an improvement in the rule of law represents an essential foundation for attracting foreign investment and supporting local innovation, increasing the potential for economic and social development. On

the other hand, some countries have experienced significant declines. Among these, Cyprus, Malta, and Italy stand out, with reductions of 19%, 16%, and 10%, respectively. Particularly, traditionally stable countries such as the United Kingdom and France have seen respective declines of 7.9% and 8%, possibly reflecting growing distrust in legal institutions or perceived inefficiencies in judicial systems. The United States, also down by 9.5%, reflects possible challenges in maintaining an accessible and fairly applied legal system, which can negatively impact investment attractiveness and the innovation environment. Countries such as Brazil, Greece, and South Africa, which have recorded declines of around 13%, show a deterioration in the rule of law that may be linked to rising inequalities, high corruption levels, or political instability. This decline has potentially negative effects for emerging economies, as a weak and unreliable legal system discourages entrepreneurship and makes investments riskier. Situations like those in Mozambique and Nicaragua, where there has been a reduction of over 30%, highlight severe institutional issues that drastically limit economic and social development potential. Finally, countries like Finland and Singapore, while starting from a very high level, have maintained their rule of law or shown slight improvements. This suggests that for already stable and advanced countries, maintaining the rule of law requires commitment and resources to ensure institutional sustainability, a factor that contributes to strengthening market confidence and attracting innovation.

Conclusions. The Rule of Law value increased by 0.36% on average between 2013 and 2022 for the countries analyzed, rising from 50.90 to 51.09 units. The top performers are Côte d'Ivoire with +131.06%, Ecuador with +93.33%, Uzbekistan with +90.72%, Nigeria with +83.82%, and Guinea with +77.33%. The worst performers are Cyprus with -19.39%, Turkey with -25.35%, Mali with -34.22%, Mozambique with -38.94%, and Nicaragua with -48.21%.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+16>

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Performers	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Cote d'Ivoire	13,2	30,5	17,3	131,0606
	Ecuador	16,5	31,9	15,4	93,33333
	Uzbekistan	9,7	18,5	8,8	90,72165
	Nigeria	13,6	25	11,4	83,82353
	Guinea	7,5	13,3	5,8	77,33333
Worse Performers	Cyprus	75,8	61,1	-14,7	-19,3931
	Turkiye	49,3	36,8	-12,5	-25,355
	Mali	33,6	22,1	-11,5	-34,2262
	Mozambique	32,1	19,6	-12,5	-38,9408
	Nicaragua	28	14,5	-13,5	-48,2143